

On Event-Aware Manufacturing Systems

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Abstract: Manufacturing systems face different types of events, which may disrupt production and prevent them from reaching the expected production goals. Such events may arise from within production processes (e.g., machine malfunctions), from demand (e.g., urgent orders) or even from supply (e.g., delay in the delivery of critical components). Manufacturing systems need to be able to identify such disruptions in real-time, evaluate their impact to production and react timely to repair the affected processes in an automatic way. This appears plausible by utilizing Industry 4.0 enabling technologies, such as data analytics and cyber-physical systems coupled with modelling, optimisation and simulation. In this regard, we focus our study on event-aware manufacturing systems and address the challenge of designing and implementing them. To do so, we follow a design science approach which enables us to frame the scope of identification and handling of disruptions in two manufacturing case studies, categorise the requirements provided by the corresponding manufacturers, identify the major functionalities to be supported by such a system and designate the technical specification for all its core modules and the system as a whole.

Keywords: smart manufacturing, Industry 4.0, event-driven architecture, decision support systems, event-aware manufacturing systems

1. MOTIVATION

Event management systems for supply chains have emerged to provide functionality for monitoring schedules, managing disruptions and repairing schedules affected by a disruptive event. (Fernández et al., 2015). Several approaches for reactive monitoring (Liu et al., 2007; Winkelmann et al., 2009) for predictive monitoring (Kim & Choi, 2009) and for both reactive and predictive monitoring were proposed. From the point of view of data collecting capability, they can be classified into approaches for order monitoring, approaches for resource monitoring (Kim & Choi, 2009) and approaches for both order and resource monitoring (Winkelmann, et al., 2009). Monitoring systems are conceived as an extension of traditional tracking and tracing systems (Szirbik et al., 2000) with capability to collect data and to process these data in order to detect and/or anticipate disruptive events. Monitoring system capabilities rely on the monitoring process that defines the set of tasks to be performed for anticipating/detecting disruptive events (Fernández et al., 2012).

Motivated by the above and also by the notion of situation awareness, this paper introduces event-aware manufacturing systems, i.e., systems that interpret and exploit pieces of raw information (e.g., sensor data) within a higher, domain-relevant concept called situation, i.e., an abstract state of affairs pertinent to specific applications. In the context of

enterprise computing systems, the ‘situation’ is defined as an event occurrence that might require a reaction (Endsley, 2016). The main differentiation with the event management systems for supply chains is that event-aware manufacturing systems extend their scope beyond the typical reactive and/or predictive event monitoring to place strong emphasis on supporting decision making and action taking, hence covering the five discrete steps of Endsley (2016) regarding situation awareness.

Moreover, several recent approaches highlight both the need and the plausible directions for a contemporary toolset that effectively handles several disruptions in the plant floor, from machine failures to delayed deliveries and low quality of components. To move beyond the current state of the art, we utilise the fact that ICT-based systems and service platforms play a major role in the current industrial transformation: they bring connectivity and enable monitoring, analysing, simulating, optimising and controlling production entities and processes, thus creating a virtual copy of the physical world and facilitating decentralised structures through Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS).

Our work is also influenced by the current shift in the traditional automation pyramid, which has been based on a layered structure of automation systems: machines are controlled by logical devices (e.g., PCs, PLCs, PIDs), which are supervised by control and data acquisition systems (SCADA) and then MES and ERP at the higher level

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'planning levels'. In contrast to this layered scheme, current developments move towards a lean architecture, within which components and actors may interact in flexible and arbitrary fashions, loosely orchestrated by some system controller, e.g., for reasons of data integrity or security.

2. CONTEXT

Our inspiration is not purely academic but actually originates from an industry-led research project called DISRUPT¹. Therefore, our approach bridges coherent requirements and use-cases from modern manufacturing with the capacities of existing research and software. By applying a design science approach (Peffer et al., 2007), we obtain a minimal technical specification, or, alternatively, an archetype instantiation of an integrated system that is close to the Industry 4.0 idea and has been validated by actors in the real world.

The two manufactures initially defining DISRUPT are FCA, an Italian car manufacturer and ARCELIK, a Turkish white goods and electronics manufacturer, both being global actors facing all the major challenges of modern distributed and massively-customised production. The two end-users offer quite distinct business cases and problems, which appear old-fashioned at first sight, yet remain unresolved. In brief, FCA's assembly plants work constantly at a fixed 'cars-per-hour' rate, which is however distracted by some low machine performance (e.g., car painting) but, mostly, from delays in the delivery of critical car components (these components are delivered just before being assembled to minimise inventory); that is, although at a fully automated plant, the production manager cannot foresee such delay and, most important, estimate their impact react accordingly. Hence FCA asks for an event-aware system handling outer plant disruptions but possibly inner ones, at a quite homogeneous production process.

To the contrary, ARCELIK operates several plants producing PCBs (printed circuit board) for white goods. Here, disruptions come from (i) the volatility in the cycle time of the testing phase in PCB production and (ii) the changes in the orders of other ARCELIK plants producing white goods thus issuing orders to the PCB-producing plant. Thus, ARCELIK faces also both inner and outer disruptions therefore requiring decision support several times during a shift and, in addition, tighter coordination with other plants.

3. CONTRIBUTION

Given the above, this paper contributes to the current discourse of Industry 4.0 in several terms. The most obvious is the approach itself, in the sense of applying design science in this context and using two quite demanding and representative business cases. Then comes the elicitation of requirements and their grouping into a rather generic manner which makes them transferrable in similar contexts and offers evidence on the innovative features of the topics examined here. The categories encompassing all use cases are (i) monitoring the in-bound logistics and production processes (ii) capture events and generate alerts, (iii) quantify the impact of identified events on the current plan (iv) provide alternatives for handling the events, (v) evaluate alternatives,

(vi) actualize the selected alternatives and (vii) model the manufacturing knowledge.

That is, these requirements and the associated use-cases, illustrate in a convincing way the necessity of deploying several technologies alongside 'industrial internet of things' and CPS; it possibly highlights also their sufficiency given the generic nature of the use cases examined. Most critically, we continue the process of devising an integrated manufacturing system by showing in detail the logical view of the system itself, in terms of main functionalities, core behaviour of different modules and a minimal set of the interconnections among them. The modules discussed via this logical view are Complex Event Processing and Predictive Analytics, CPS, Modelling, Simulation and Optimisation as well as their Orchestration. The overall system has been developed in a prototype form and validated by manufacturers via direct demonstration.

Overall, this paper adopts an end-to-end design science approach for a contemporary manufacturing system that uses novel methods to solve old problems. Through real business cases and a grouping of use cases in relevance to Industry 4.0, it addresses recent calls for exemplars in design science research (Peffer et al., 2007), while, through a logical view possibly transferable beyond our context, it realises a clear interplay between monitoring, decision support and actualization that handles events in a 'situationally-aware' manner.

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